

Analyzing Bagmati's decline in water quality, environmental and health risks in comparison to previous records

Anish P. Lohani*, Adit P. Lohani**

*Budhanilkantha School

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7686798
<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686798>

Table of Contents

1) Abstract	1
2) Introduction	4
2.1) History of the Bagmati River.....	5
2.2) Significance of Bagmati River.....	6
3) Initiatives for Bagmati River Conservation	1
3.1) The Bagmati River Basin Improvement Project (BRBIP).....	2
3.2) The Bagmati River Cleanup Campaign.....	3
3.3) Pashupati Area Development Trust (PADT).....	3
3.4) National Trust for Nature Conservation (NTNC).....	3
3.5) United Nations Park Development Committee.....	3
3.6) Nepal River Conservation Trust	3
3.7) Analysis of Previous Research	3
4) Comparison of Cleaning the Bagmati River with Other Rivers	4
4.1) River Thames in Britain.....	5
4.2) River Kallang in Singapore.....	6
4.3) Rhine River in Europe	6
4.4) Qinhuai River in China	6
5) Methodology	1
5.1) Research Questions.....	2
5.2) Study Area	3
5.3) Data Collection and Bibliography	4

Abstract- Biological monitoring techniques are useful in the field of environmental health for assessing the risk of toxic agents. Bagmati, a river in Nepal is home to many toxic chemicals and pollutions. As a result of direct drainage to Bagmati, domestic wastes, industrial wastes and many other factors, Bagmati has been very polluted. As a result it has contaminated many places nearby and also the river flows directly into the oceans. So In this report we have presented you the history of river and all the pollution contributors. We have also remarked the possible solutions and have also compared the river with some rivers worldwide.

1 INTRODUCTION

1a HISTORY OF THE BAGMATI RIVER

Bagmati river is the largest river in Kathmandu Valley. The river originates from Shivapuri Hill, 25 km north of the city at an altitude of 2650 m above sea level. (Fig. 1.1) There are altogether 13 tributaries among which the major ones include Bishnumati, Dhobikhola, Manohara, Tukucha, Nakkhu, Hanumante, Dally and Balkhu (Fig. 1.2). The river flows along a length of 29 km. The river flows along a length of 29km through the valley, and separates two Major districts of Nepal; Kathmandu and Lalitpur districts. It is the main river of Bagmati Basin. Bagmati Basin is a major tributary of the Ganges river and has a catchment area of 3610 km², which is 2.25% of the total area of Nepal. (Health and Environmental Management Society, 2016)

Figure1-1. Location Map

Source: Water 2019, 11, 1416; doi:10.3390/w11071416

Figure 1.2 Tributaries of the Bagmati River

Source: Kannel, Prakash & Lee, Seockheon & Lee, Young-Soo & Kanel, Sushil & Khan, Siddhi. (2007). Application of Water Quality Indices and Dissolved Oxygen as Indicators for River Water Classification and Urban Impact Assessment. Environmental monitoring and assessment. 132. 93-110. 10.1007/s10661-006-9505-1.

The Bagmati basin includes eight districts: Kathmandu, Lalitpur, Bhaktapur, Makawanpur, Kavre, Sindhuli, Rautahat and Sarlahi. Based on topography and land use, the basin is divided into three sub-basins: the Upper Bagmati basin (662 km²), the Middle Bagmati basin, and the Lower Bagmati basin. This research will concentrate on the Upper Bagmati basin, which is a section of the Bagmati River in Kathmandu Valley. The climate in this basin is subtropical in the valley and foothills (20 °C–30 °C), moderate and temperate in the mid-elevation (15 °C–20 °C), and chilly in the higher mountains (10 °C–15 °C). Rain and snow are the primary sources of input into the Bagmati Basin. The basin receives an average of 1800 mm of rain per annum, with the monsoon season (June–September) accounting for 90% of the precipitation (Bosch & Hewlett, 1982; Odum, 1971). From its upper basin, the river supplies the majority of the city of Kathmandu's drinking water.

The valley has a population of 2.5 million people, with a 4.63 percent annual growth rate (Urban Pathways, 2020). This equates to 9.32% of Nepal's population. Surface water in Kathmandu Valley is heavily contaminated by industrial effluent, domestic garbage, and untreated sewage discharged from residential areas (MP DRAFT 3). In Kathmandu, over 40 million liters of waste water are created everyday, with homes accounting for 80 percent of this total (Pandey, 2005). Data on solid waste production are hard to come by. In 2012, Kathmandu Valley municipalities generated an estimated 626,700 kg of solid trash (Kathmandu Upatyaka Khanepani Limited, Ministry of Urban Development, & Government of Nepal, 2013). According to a 2003 research conducted by the Asian Development Bank and the International Center for Integrated Mountain Development, cities in the Kathmandu Valley discharged 21,000 kg of residential sewage daily into the Bagmati River, accounting for 42% of its total BOD load (Batra, 2015). The amount of industrial pollution being discharged directly into the river was growing; 3,151 kg of industrial BOD load was released directly into the river per day (CEMAT Consultants, 2000).

1B SIGNIFICANCE OF THE BAGMATI RIVER

Early civilisation in Kathmandu Valley began (between 167 BC and 1 AD) along the banks of the Bagmati River near the Pashupatinath Temple and on the banks of the Dhobikhola at Hadigaon (Kathmandu Valley Environment Outlook, 2007). People began to settle in the valley because it was fertile (lacustrine soil) and abundant in natural resources (limestones, water resource, grass land suitable for cattle)

The Bagmati River is revered by both Hindus and Buddhists, and several old Hindu sanctuaries can be found on both banks of the river. This river is culturally and economically valuable to the inhabitants of Kathmandu. However, Kathmandu Valley's fast and unplanned development has raised water consumption. This, along with a lack of solid waste and waste water treatment facilities, has resulted in health risks. As a result, cultural and recreational activities, such as traditional rites performed along river banks, have declined (Project Administration Manual for Nepal: Bagmati River Basin Improvement Project, 2013).

2 Initiatives for Bagmati River Conservation:

Since the mid-1990s, many programs have been undertaken to clean and protect the Bagmati River, with the majority of them yielding minimal benefits. Some of the most important are listed here.

2A THE BAGMATI RIVER BASIN IMPROVEMENT PROJECT (BRBIP)

The Government of Nepal (GON) has long endeavored, with limited success, to remedy the deterioration of the Bagmati River basin. The BRBIP featured adequate legislative and institutional frameworks for implementing integrated water resource management, which could be duplicated for other basins in the nation. Water resource planning, development, and management in the Bagmati River basin have been haphazard and disorganized. Government agencies worked in silos, resulting in inefficient investments and inequitable water distribution for human needs and the environment. These elements have a significant impact on the government's development efforts to increase water security in the basin (Project Administration Manual for Nepal: Bagmati River Basin Improvement Project, 2013). The first phase of the BRBIP ran from May 2014 to May 2019 and had the following objectives:

- establish systems and capacity for integrated and participatory river basin management;
- improve the river bank environment in the urban area;
- increase water availability in the basin during the dry season and improve watershed conservation;
- establish a flood forecasting and early warning system for the Bagmati River basin;
- increase project management efficiency with efficacy.

The project was just halfway finished. This report is concerned with targets (b) and (c). Target (b) was to be accomplished by constructing 7.2 km of river-corridor construction with aesthetically pleasing river barriers, green zones, and recreational amenities — of which only 1 km was built in the Sinamangal portion. Work in the other areas is 70% complete. The construction of 11 aeration weirs and the refurbishment of two regulators has been completed. Target (c) was to be reached by building the 95-meter-high Dhap Dam at the Bagmati River's headwaters, farther upstream of Sundarikal (one of the sites utilized in this study—see Section 4 on Methodology), with an 85,000-m³ storage capacity, mainly to assist flush the waste downstream. The Dhap-Dam is only half finished.

The BRBIP's second phase began in December 2019 and will be finished in November 2024. It will bring the Dhap Dam project to a close. The project will also finish the remaining 6.2 kilometers of river corridors, including landscaping and restoration of 23 historic and cultural monuments on the river banks, as well as build and operate a waste water treatment plant (WWTP) to clean the polluted water of the Tukucha tributary that flows into the Bagmati River. Every day, about 17 million liters of treated effluent will be discharged into the river, contributing to an increase in Bagmati River flow during the dry season (Asian Development Bank, 2017).

2B THE BAGMATI RIVER CLEANUP CAMPAIGN

The Bagmati River Cleanup Campaign, a citizen-led project in Kathmandu, began in May 2013. It is a separate movement that is not affiliated with BRBIP; volunteers collect solid garbage from the river that has been deposited by houses and businesses. The continuing cleanliness drive is solely a social endeavor of groups attempting to

enhance the livability of Kathmandu. The GON, Nepal Police, Nepal Army, Kathmandu Metropolitan City, and foreign nonprofit groups such as Lions International have all sponsored the initiative. Celebrities, MP DRAFT 6 public figures, students, and tourists are among those who have taken part. The program has been running every Saturday (a Nepalese holiday) at 7:30 a.m. for three hours.

Mr. Leela Mani Poudel, the GON's Chief Secretary in 2013, led the effort. To commemorate the 100th week of the Bagmati Cleanup Campaign, a human chain was constructed from Sundarikal to Chovar on Saturday, April 11, 2015. Thousands of people gathered early in the morning to construct a 29-kilometer chain from Sundarikal to Chovar, including the Vice President, Prime Minister, and party leaders. As of July 2017, the cleanup drive has been organized in over 45 distinct locations, with approximately 20,000 tons of rubbish removed from the river and its banks (Vaidya, 2017). By December 2018, the campaign has enlisted the participation of over 350 organizations and 250,000 volunteers.

On October 19, 2019, for example, the river's 336th week in the campaign, more than 300 campaigners and volunteers from 15 groups took part. Six metric tons of trash were removed from the river beneath the Tripureshwar bridge. Similarly, the sections Dhobikhola, Bishnumati, Manahara, Tilganga, Sundarighat, and Gheshwari were cleansed.

As a result of the campaign, the government upgraded the sewage system that ran straight into the Bagmati River in several areas of the city, reducing pollution in the river (Adhikari, 2016).

The Kathmandu Valley Wastewater Management Project is being implemented by the Ministry of Water Supply. In Kathmandu Valley, there are five large wastewater treatment facilities (WWTPs) with a combined capacity of 32.4 million liters per day (Table 1-1). (MLD). The Guheshwari WWTP is the largest of the five and is located near the Bagmati River and the Guheshwari sample location in this research. The plant's goal is to minimize pollution in the Bagmati Water while increasing river flow to the Pashupatinath Temple for religious activities. The Guheshwari sewage is now routed through a tunnel to downstream of the Pashupatinath shrine since the effluent quality is unsuitable.

Table 1- 1. Existing WWTPs

Parameter	WWTP				
	Hanumanghat	Sallaghari	Kodku	Dhobighat	Guheshwari
Year established	1975	1983	1982	1982	2002
Reported nominal capacity (MLD)	0.5	2	1.1	15.4	16.4
Original supporting agency	GTZ Germany	GTZ Germany	IDA, Engineering Science/USA	IDA, Engineering Science/USA	Government of Nepal
Operator	KUKL	KUKL	KUKL	KUKL	HPCIDBC
Type of plant originally installed	Aerated lagoon	Aerated lagoon	Waste stabilization pond	Waste stabilization pond	Oxidation ditch
Catchment served	North-east Bhaktapur	North & south Bhaktapur	East Lalitpur	Kathmandu and Lalitpur	Gokarna & Chabahil
Existing operation status	Treatment significantly below design intentions	Treatment significantly below design intentions	Treatment significantly below design intentions	Not operational since 1982	Treatment significantly below design intentions

Source: Asian Development Bank (January 2013)

2C PASHUPATI AREA DEVELOPMENT TRUST (PADT)

The Pashupati Area Development Trust was formed in 1990 to undertake protection and administration of the Pashupatinath Temple and its 264-hectare surrounding area (ha). PADT has devised a strategy for the preservation and development of the Pashupatinath Temple

region in order to reduce the consequences of urbanization, commercialization, and unplanned construction surrounding the temple.

2D NATIONAL TRUST FOR NATURE CONSERVATION (NTNC)

The Bagmati Action Plan was developed in 2008 by the NTNC (formerly the King Mahendra Trust for Nature Conservation), with the goal of rehabilitating and restoring the Bagmati River and its habitat (NWCF, 2009).

2E UNITED NATIONS PARK DEVELOPMENT COMMITTEE

The UN Park Development Committee was formed in 1995 to oversee the development of the UN Park along the Bagmati River. Representatives from ministries, civic society, and the corporate sector served on the working committee. The UN Park project was launched to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the UN office's foundation in Nepal. They constructed a green belt, which included the UN Park, along a 3.5-kilometer section of the Bagmati River from Shankhamul to the Teku River confluence (Teku Dovan).

2F NEPAL RIVER CONSERVATION TRUST (NRCT)

A group of river tourism guides created the Nepal River Conservation Trust in 1995. To raise conservation awareness and promote environmental sustainability, the NRCT has hosted the Bagmati River Festival and other yearly river festivals. Similarly, Friends of Bagmati was founded in 2000 to promote awareness and undertake river cleanup initiatives on a regular basis. FOB is made up of people from many walks of life who have joined together because they have a similar concern and a desire to restore the ecology of the Bagmati River and other rivers in Nepal.

2G ANALYSIS OF PREVIOUS RESEARCH

Many researchers have researched the physicochemical parameters and biological-indicators of the Bagmati River, which revealed increased pollution of the Bagmati River and worsening of water quality with growing population density in Kathmandu Valley, according to Dahal, Khanal, and Ale (2011). As a result, the indigenous aquatic wildlife communities have vanished (Dahal et al., 2011). According to more recent assessments, the river's condition has improved since 2013. From September 2014 to February 2015, turbidity, biological oxygen demand (BOD), and chemical oxygen demand (COD) reduced, but dissolved oxygen (DO) rose, according to Prajapati (2015). Similarly, Bhandari, Joshi, Shrestha, and Nakarmi (2017) stated "a modest decrease in pollution was seen in 2013 and 2014 data, perhaps due to the Bagmati River Cleanup Campaign."

3.1 COMPARISON OF CLEANING THE BAGMATI RIVER WITH OTHER RIVER

3.1.1 RIVER THAMES IN BRITAIN

In 1957, the Thames River was deemed biologically dead. Wartime bombs, according to Hardach (2015), had damaged parts of the original Victorian sewers that had previously helped keep the river clean. Postwar Britain lacked the resources to address the issue promptly. Only in the late 1960s, when London's sewage system steadily improved alongside the country's overall postwar recovery, did the Thames start to breathe again. Concerns over pesticides and fertilizer poured into Britain's rivers with every downpour developed in the 1970s and 1980s, as part of a wider growth in environmental consciousness. Tighter controls followed, causing harmful metal levels in the river to fall. The Thames has 125 species of fish in 2015, up from nearly none in the 1950s.

3.1.2 RIVER KALLANG IN SINGAPORE

Between 1977 and 1987, the Singapore River and Kallang basin were cleaned. The cleanup included physical cleaning of heavily polluted rivers, the removal of various sources of pollution, the provision of proper sewage infrastructure, new facilities for resettled residents and businesses, and the implementation of anti-pollution measures to minimize future pollution, according to Singapore Infopedia (2019).

3.1.3 RHINE RIVER IN EUROPE

The Rhine River Restoration Project in Europe is a wonderful example of how individuals from Switzerland, France, Germany, and the Netherlands worked together to restore the river. This snow-fed river enjoyed a constant and high flow of water, which supported trade, shipping, urbanization, and industrialisation along its banks for centuries. The river has deteriorated as a result of these changes. Because 20 million people rely on this river for drinking water, it was critical to keep the river's water quality and ecology in good shape. The four nations banded together to make significant investments in sewage treatment systems. Changes in manufacturing techniques and the development of wastewater treatment facilities were also made by industries along the river's bank in order to safeguard the river. Multiple solutions were adopted in a variety of local communities across the four nations, in addition to government and industry funding. The river that was formerly known as the "sewer of Europe" was restored and rediscovered as a result of these endeavors (NWCF, 2009).

3.1.4 QINHUI RIVER IN CHINA

Another example, comparable to the Bagmati River in Nepal, is the Qinhuai River in China. The quality of human settlement and the urban environment in Nanjing had been badly harmed by illegal slums and squatters' colonies along the river's channel, as well as the dirty river environment and the terrible odor of the river water. At the end of 2002, the government launched the Qinhuai MP DRAFT 11 River Rehabilitation Program, which aimed to enhance the river's ecosystem via a variety of conservation and restoration efforts. The first phase of the project, which began in 2005, entailed the removal and resettlement of 4356 homes in a 380-square-meter area along the river. Along the river's course, a total of 22 kilometers of wastewater interception pipeline was installed. In 2006, the second phase of river rehabilitation began. The Nanjing-Qinhuai river has been transformed into a historical, cultural, and tourism destination (Bajracharya, 2009).

4 Methodology

4.1 Research Questions

This research seeks to analyze the water quality of the Bagmati River in light of its importance, deterioration of its water quality, and environmental and health risks using secondary sources of data. The study question is: "How does the present water quality of the Bagmati River compare to past measurements?"

4.2 Study Area

This research focuses on a 29-kilometer stretch of the Bagmati River inside Kathmandu Valley, from Sundarijal (27.761830, 85.422604) to Chovar (27.761830, 85.422604). (27.658102, 85.293544). Chovar is the exit of the Bagmati River watershed, which drains an area of 595.4 km². The basin's elevation ranges from 1178 to 2723 meters above sea level. Natural springs and yearly rainfall are the river's primary water sources. The study region receives an average yearly rainfall of 1900 mm. During the monsoon season, almost 80% of the rainfall occurs (July - September). The river basin is 650 km² in size, with elevations varying from 1220 to 2800 meters above sea level (Khanal et al., 2007). The climate in the basin is mild temperate, with summer temperatures ranging from 19 to 27 degrees Celsius and winter temperatures ranging from 2 to 20 degrees Celsius (NTNC, 2009). At Khokana, the river has an annual average flow of 17.7 m³ /s, with a seven-day minimum of 1.31 m³ /s (Kannel, Lee, Kanel, Kahn, & Lee, 2007). After the monsoon, the river flow decreases significantly, yet untreated solid and liquid wastes are still discharged into the river, assuming that the water would transport them away. The volume of garbage has increased in proportion to the increase in the number and size of the communities. As a result, the river's low flow during non-monsoon months can no longer flush the garbage away (NWCF, 2009).

DATA COLLECTION

Data from secondary sources was gathered from a variety of sources. The majority of the data was gathered from the High Powered

Committee for Integrated Development of the Bagmati Civilization |
 Bagmati River Water Quality Test Report | Download Categories |
 Beside these, data from Rana M.P. et al. (2019), Thakur J.K. et al.
 (2017) , Kandel et al. (2007) were also collected compiled and analyzed.

Sample site	Coordinates		Characteristics
Sundarijal	27.761830	85.422604	Upper portion of river, just outside the national park, minimum human influence
Gokarna	27.739223	85.387933	Mixing of seasonal rivers and some sewage pipe, dense human settlement
Guheshwari Ghat	27.711287	85.354190	Protected area on one side and dense human settlement on the other side
Gaurighat	27.712949	85.349580	Protected area on one side and dense human settlement on the other side; upstream of religious site (Pashupatinath Temple) and cremation area (Arya Ghat)
Tilganga	27.702621	85.349980	Downstream of religious site (Pashupatinath Temple) with cremation area (Arya Ghat), human/industrial waste mixed with sewage
Sankhamul Ghat	27.680574	85.329980	After joining of the Manahara and Hanumante Rivers
Tripureshwar	27.691834	85.310742	After the squatter settlement, sewage and garbage dumping into the river in Thapathali and after joining of the Dhobi River and Tukucha River
Teku Dovan	27.691236	85.301912	Lower stretch of the river after joining of the Bishnumati River
Balkhu Dovan	27.681765	85.299020	Lower stretch of river after joining of the Balkhu River

Fig 4.1

Fig 4.2

Locations (Places)

a. Sundarijal

Sundarijal is 15 kilometers distant from the city core. The Bagmati River originates in this area, and the Shivapuri National Park is on its northern bank. Sundarijal is 5.18 km² (2 sq mi) in size. Sundarijal is where the Shyalmati and Nagmati rivers meet the Bagmati River. Sundarijal has a population of 2552 people living in 547 houses according to the 2011 Nepal Census. Hikers can begin their journey to the Langtang range and the 22-kilometer Sundarijal-Chisapani climb from here.

Fig 4.3

b. Gokarna

The Bagmati River runs alongside Mahadev Temple, which was completed in 1582. From late August to early September, people come to this shrine to pay their respects to their departed fathers. According to the Nepali census, the municipality has a population of 107,351.

c. Guheshwari ghat

Guheshwari Temple is a popular pilgrimage place for both Hindus and Buddhists. It's eleven kilometers east of Pashupatinath Temple, and it's in a rather safe neighborhood. It has an activated sludge facility, which is the only one of the five waste water treatment facilities that have been functioning since 2003. The northern and eastern parts of this region are densely populated.

d. Gaurighat

Gaurighat is a historic city on the Bagmati River's western bank. It is located to the north of Pashupatinath Temple. It is in a reasonably sheltered location, however the northern and eastern sides are thickly inhabited. Guheshwari Ghat is not far away.

e. Tilganga

In contrast, Tilganga is also a thickly inhabited place. The river includes ash from the burning of dead on the Bagmati's upstream bank, where Pashupatinath Temple is located. On the east side, the monitoring station is near to Nepal's only international airport (Tribhuvan International Airport (TIA, VNKT)). The monitoring stations' south and west sides are

thickly inhabited.

f. Sankhaul ghat

Sankhamul Ghat is a half-kilometer-long embankment located upstream of the sample point, at the confluence of the Manohara and Bagmati Rivers. Because confluences are considered auspicious sites, the Sankhamul Ghat serves as the district's principal cremation site and a significant area for ceremonial bathing during the Maghe Sankranti festival. In addition, this is a thickly inhabited neighborhood.

g. Tripureswar

Upstream, the Dhobikhola River merges with the Bagmati River. On the banks of the Bagmati river at Tripureswar, there is a notable 19th century temple dedicated to Mahadev, a Hindu god. In addition, it is a thickly inhabited neighborhood.

h. Teku Dovan

A little distance upstream, the Bishnumati River meets the Bagmati River. Dead people are cremated on its banks because this is also a confluence. Teku Dovan is also a crowded neighbourhood.

i. Balkhu

Balkhu Khol is a watercourse in Nepal that rises to a height of 1,287 meters. Balkhu Khol is located south of the Bisnumati River, near Tribhuvan University. Balkhu has a dense population.

j. Chovar

Chobhar (or Chovar, or Chobar) is located 9 kilometers southwest of Kathmandu in the Kirtipur Municipality. This is a crowded neighborhood. Nepal had a population of 5,627 people living in 1,109 households at the time of the 1991 census. Chobhar is notable for the Chobhar caves, which are located near the Chobhar Gorge (gorge where the Bagmati River departs the Valley). There is also a temple dedicated to both Buddhists and Hindus, Jal Binayak Temple and Adinath Lokeshwar And Chobhar Hills. There are magnificent flora and suburbs, as well as limestone, that enhance to the town's charm. Water supply and the tourist attraction Manjushree Park are two of the village's main sources of revenue.

WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS

Parameters compared

Parameter	Unit
pH Readings	-
Turbidity	NTU
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	mg/L
Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	mg/L
Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	mg/L
E-coli	CFU/100 ml

Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Lower temperatures result in higher amounts of dissolved oxygen (DO), whereas warmer waters result in lower levels of DO. Dissolved oxygen concentrations in healthy water should be between 6.5 and 8 mg/L. During the monsoon, the DO varied from 4 to 9 mg/L, and after the monsoon, it ranged from 1 to 16 mg/L. Gaurighat had the highest DO levels in both seasons, at 9 and 16 mg/L, respectively. Sundarijal had the greatest amount of DO after Gaurighat, with 8 mg/L during the monsoon and 9 mg/L after the monsoon. DOs of 1 mg/L were found in Shankhamul Ghat and Tripureshwar (Figure 5-3).

Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)

The quantity of dissolved oxygen (DO) consumed by aerobic microbes when digesting organic materials in water is measured by BOD. During the monsoon, BOD levels varied from 3 to 106 mg/L, and after the monsoon, BOD levels were less than 1 to 90 mg/L. During both seasons, Sundarijal had the lowest BOD, whereas Tilganga had the highest, with 106 mg/L during the monsoon. BODs were from 65 to 90 mg/L in Sankhamul Ghat, Tripureshwar, Teku Dovan, and Balkhu Dovan (Figure 4-4).

5 Results and Discussion

Results of parameters

pH

Monsoon and post-monsoon pH levels varied from 5.9 to 7.1 and 6.9 to 7.5, respectively. In all sample locations, the overall pH levels throughout the post monsoon are higher than those in the monsoon. During the monsoon, the pH was slightly acidic in all areas except Balkhu, and slightly alkaline in all locations except Gaurighat and Guheshwari Ghat during the post monsoon. It fluctuated between 5.9 and 7.1 mg/L during the monsoon and 6.9 and 7.5 mg/L after the monsoon (see Figure 5-1)

(source: Rana MP et al.)

Turbidity

During the monsoon, turbidity varied from 26 to 85 NTU, with 26 NTU in Sundarijal and 85 NTU at Balkhu Dovan. However, at Sundarijal and Tripureshwar, it varied from 5 to 390 NTU during the post-monsoon period. The turbidity in Sankhamul Ghat and Teku Dovan was 183 NTU and 182 NTU, respectively, roughly half that of Tripureshwar (Figure 5-2).

Chemical Oxygen Demand

Bacteria

Thirteen water samples were taken from three Bagmati River locations and submitted to Illumina MiSeq sequencing, yielding an average of 97,412 35,909 16S rRNA gene sequences per sample. Proteobacteria (59–80 percent) was the most prevalent phylum in all of the samples, followed by Bacteroidetes (10–25 percent) and Firmicutes (6–15 percent), as shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows that of the 61 classes discovered, Epsilonproteobacteria (29–57%) was prevalent in nine river water samples, while Betaproteobacteria (27–32%) was prominent in four river water samples. In all of the samples analyzed, the abundance ratios of the classes Gammaproteobacteria and Bacteroidia varied from 6–24 percent and 5–15 percent, respectively. Table 1 summarizes the 18 taxa that were discovered at abundance ratios of >1% in at least one of the 13 samples analyzed, out of the 111 possible pathogenic bacteria identified. At all three locations, Arcobacter was the most prevalent genus, with abundance ratios of 28.6% (n = 1), 31.3 15.8% (n = 6), and 31.8 17.2% (n = 6) at Sundarrijal, Thapathali, and Chovar, respectively. Acinetobacter abundance ratios were 10.3 percent, 5.3 percent, and 5.0 3.9 percent, respectively, in Sundarrijal, Thapathali, and Chovar, whereas Prevotella abundance ratios were 5.9 percent, 6.8 2.4 percent, and 4.6 1.5 percent, respectively. Thapathali and Chovar, respectively. Acinetobacter abundance ratios were 10.3 percent, 5.3 percent, and 5.0 3.9 percent at Sundarrijal, Thapathali, and Chovar, respectively, whereas Prevotella abundance ratios were 5.9 percent, 6.8 2.4 percent, and 4.6 percent at Sundarrijal, Thapathali, and Chovar, respectively. (Thakur J.K. et al. (2017))

Figure 3. Distribution of bacterial classes.

Table 1. Abundance ratios of potential pathogenic bacteria.

Genus	Abundance Ratio (%)		
	Sundarrijal (n = 1)	Thapathali (n = 6)	Chovar (n = 6)
<i>Acidovorax</i>	2.2	1.0 ± 0.8	1.1 ± 0.6
<i>Acinetobacter</i>	10.3	5.3 ± 5.3	5.0 ± 3.9
<i>Arcobacter</i>	28.6	31.3 ± 15.8	31.8 ± 17.2
<i>Bacteroides</i>	1.7	2.6 ± 0.9	2.3 ± 1.1
<i>Blautia</i>	0.4	0.8 ± 0.4	0.7 ± 0.6
<i>Burkholderia</i>	0.3	0.5 ± 0.6	0.5 ± 0.2
<i>Chromobacterium</i>	0.4	0.4 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.5
<i>Chryseobacterium</i>	1.4	0.9 ± 0.6	1.5 ± 1.0
<i>Clostridium</i>	0.3	0.7 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.3
<i>Comamonas</i>	2.1	1.1 ± 1.4	1.0 ± 0.7
<i>Escherichia</i>	1.1	0.4 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.1
<i>Flavobacterium</i>	4.7	3.0 ± 4.3	3.4 ± 3.9
<i>Mycobacterium</i>	0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.8
<i>Parabacteroides</i>	0.4	0.8 ± 0.7	1.1 ± 0.9
<i>Plesiomonas</i>	2.2	1.2 ± 0.6	1.5 ± 0.7
<i>Prevotella</i>	5.9	6.8 ± 2.4	4.6 ± 1.5
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	1.6	1.6 ± 0.9	1.8 ± 1.0
<i>Sphingobacterium</i>	1.9	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1

3.2. Occurrence of Total Bacteria and Arcobacter in River Water Samples

The total bacteria and Arcobacter levels in six river water samples from Sundarrijal, Thapathali, and Chovar were assessed using qPCR, as shown in Figure 4. The minimum and highest total bacteria concentrations were 7.1 and 10.5 log₁₀ copies/100 mL, respectively, for the three locations. Arcobacter was found in two (33 percent), six (100 percent), and six (100 percent) river water samples in Sundarrijal, Thapathali, and Chovar, with concentrations of 6.7–10.4, 9.0–10.4, and 8.4–10.7 log₁₀ copies/100 mL, respectively.

Figure 2. Distribution of bacterial phyla.

Figure 4. Concentrations of 16S rRNA genes of total bacteria and Arcobacter.

E. Coli

During the monsoon, E. coli levels varied from 210 to more than 1100, with Teku Dovan having 210 and Sundarrijal, Gokarna, Tilganga, and Chovar having more than 1100. With the exception of Sundarrijal, all areas had above 1100 after the monsoon. It was 1100 degrees in Sundarrijal (Table 5-1)

Table 5- 1. E. coli

SN	Monitoring sites	Monsoon (CFU/100 ml)	Post-monsoon (CFU/100 ml)
1	Sundarijal	>1100	1100
2	Gokarna	>1100	>1100
3	Guheshwari Ghat	460	>1100
4	Gaurighat	1100	>1100
5	Tilganga	>1100	>1100
6	Sankhamul Ghat	>1100	>1100
7	Tripureshwar	1100	>1100
8	Tekhu Dovan	210	>1100
9	Balkhu Dovan	460	>1100
10	Chovar	>1100	>1100

DISCUSSION OF SEASONAL VARIATION BY SITE

pH

The water was somewhat alkaline during the post monsoon compared to the monsoon, which might be attributed to the reduced water level in the river after the monsoon. Fish can survive at these pH values since most aquatic animals prefer a pH range of 6.5 to 9.0, while some can live in water with pH levels outside of this range.

Turbidity

Because Sundarijal was the most upstream location, the water had not yet combined with many pollutants, but Balkhu Dovan, which was closer to the downstream area, had already mixed with pollutants; hence, turbidity may have been lower in Sundarijal and greater in Balkhu Dovan during monsoon. Sundarijal has the lowest turbidity in the post-monsoon period for the same reasons. Tripureshwar had the greatest turbidity value in the post-monsoon, which might be ascribed to the fact that it is located in a highly populated region just downstream of the squatter colonies. The turbidity at Sankhamul Ghat and Teku Dovan was about half that in Tripureshwar, possibly due to the closeness of the Manohara River and Bishnumati River, which brought in additional water to dilute the pollution levels in the Bagmati River. Chovar's turbidity was equivalent to that of Sankhamul Ghat and Teku Dovan, and the higher figure might be attributed to the presence of algae in the river.

DO

DO levels were greatest in Gaurighat in both seasons, at 9 and 16 mg/L, respectively. The higher value during the monsoon may be attributable to the Guheshwari WWTP discharging wastewater somewhat upstream of the Gaurighat sample location, as well as the fact that settlements are only on one side of the river bank. Sundarijal recorded the highest DO levels in both seasons after Gaurighat, which might be owing to Sundarija's small population. During the monsoon, Sankhamul Ghat and Teku Dovan had the lowest DO, whereas Teku Dovan had no DO after the monsoon. DOs of 1 mg/L were found in Shankhamul-Ghat and Tripureshwar. The heavily inhabited sections of these places, from which untreated water and solid waste is thrown into the river, may be to blame for the extremely low DO values.

BOD

In both seasons, Sundarijal had the lowest BOD, whereas Tilganga had the highest during the monsoon. Sundarijal is upstream and in a sparsely inhabited region, but Tilganga, Sankhamul Ghat, Tripureshwar, Teku Dovan, and Balkhu Dovan are downstream and in heavily populated areas, hence their BOD values are greater.

COD

The higher value in the monsoon at Tilganga might be owing to its position downstream of Pashupatinath Temple, where a large number of cremations occur, releasing pollutants. Sundarijal had the lowest value in the post-monsoon period, which might be due to its remote position. The higher result at Teku Dovan during the monsoon may be due to the cremation place, which is located slightly upstream and is in a heavily inhabited region.

E. Coli

All of the areas were infected with E. coli, making them dangerous to humans. The relatively large creek Bishnumati joining slightly upstream of the test location and moving the pollution away might be related to the lowest concentration of E. coli at Teku Dovan during the monsoon. During the monsoon, the other spots with E. coli counts of above 1100 were in highly inhabited regions where the river was too small to convey the pollution away.

5.3 TREND IN PARAMETERS DURING 2012 – 2019

Sundarijal

In the monsoon of 2012, the water in Sundarijal was more acidic than in the previous year. BOD increased marginally from 2012, whereas COD increased dramatically from 2.1 mg/L in 2014 to 40 mg/L in 2015. However, there is a variation in pH levels, a modest drop in BOD, and a significant fall in COD in the postmonsoon. Because Sundarijal is becoming more urbanized each year, it's possible that increased COD readings were found. However, both BOD and COD exhibit a declining tendency in the post-monsoon period (see Figure 5-6, 5-7 and 5-8)

Figure 5-6. pH Reading at Sundarijal

Figure 5-8. BOD & COD in Post-Monsoon Sundarjal

Figure 5-10. BOD & COD in monsoon Gokarna

GOKARNA

Despite the fact that the pH readings for both seasons have improved marginally since 2012, they have changed throughout the years. In the monsoon and post-monsoon, BOD declined marginally, but COD surged in the monsoon of 2019 but decreased somewhat in the post-monsoon. The rise in COD during the monsoon season might be due to sampling taking place a few days after the religious holiday of Father's Day, when worshippers throw all types of offerings into the river, thereby increasing COD levels (see Figure 5-9, 5-10 and 5-11). Similarly, due to pollutant in the atmosphere and prevalence of acid rain the COD might have increased.

Gaurighat

Since 2012, both monsoon and post-monsoon pH readings have improved modestly. Despite the fact that both BOD and COD have decreased since 2012, COD has grown dramatically from 12.5 mg/L in 2014 to 40 mg/L in the 2019 monsoon. However, following the monsoon, BOD and COD levels drop dramatically in 2013 and then gradually thereafter. (See Figures 5-12, 5-13, and 5-14 for further information.)

Figure 5-9. pH Readings Gokarna

Figure 5-12. pH Readings Gaurighat

Figure 5-11. BOD & COD in post-monsoon Gokarna

Figure 5-14. BOD & COD in Post-monsoon Gaurighat

Figure 5-13. BOD & COD in Monsoon Gaurighat

Shankhamul Ghat

For both seasons, the pH levels have improved. This suggests that acidity of the water has decreased (acidic nature from uric acid, inorganic acid, inorganic oxides has decreased). Even though both BOD and COD climbed dramatically from 2012 to 2013, they have reduced for both seasons in 2013. (See Figures 5-15, 5-16, and 5-17 for further information.)

Figure 5-15. pH Readings Sankhamul Ghat

Figure 5-16. BOD & COD in Monsoon Sankhamul Ghat

Figure 5-17. BOD & COD in Post-monsoon Sankhamul Ghat

Tripureshwor

The pH readings haven't altered much since 2012, however they did drop after the rain in 2013. In the monsoon, BOD and COD have been dropping since 2013, whereas in the post-monsoon, they have been decreasing since 2012. (See Figures 5-18, 5-19, and 5-20 for further information.)

Figure 5-18. pH Readings Tripureshwor

Figure 5-19. BOD & COD in Monsoon Tripureshwor

Figure 5-20. BOD & COD in Post-monsoon Tripureshwor

Balkhu

At both seasons, the pH levels in Balkhu Dovan have risen slightly from 2012. From 2013 forward, the BOD and COD were dramatically reduced during the monsoon. From 2012, the BOD and COD have been drastically lowered for the post-monsoon period. (See Figures 5-21, 5-22, and 5-23 for further information.)

Figure 5-21. pH Readings Balkhu

Figure 5-22. BOD & COD in Monsoon Balkhu

Figure 5-23. BOD & COD in Post-monsoon Balkhu

Chovar

Since 2012, the pH levels have been decreased for both seasons. BOD has a small reduction in the monsoon, but COD has a dramatic fall from 2013 forward. BOD and COD gradually decrease after the rains. (See Figures 5-24, 5-25, and 5-26 for further information.)

Figure 5-24. pH Readings Chovar

Figure 5-25. BOD & COD in Monsoon Chovar

Figure 5-26. BOD & COD in Post-monsoon Chovar

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

The water quality at upstream sites is better than at downstream ones. In both the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons, the four upstream sites – Sundarijal, Gokarna, Guheshwari Ghat, and Gaurighat – were less turbid, had greater DO, and lower BOD and COD than the six downstream sites – Tilganga, Sankhamul Ghat, Tripureshwar, Teku Dovan, Balkhu Dovan, and Chovar. Sundarijal and Guheshwari Ghat exhibited the lowest turbidity, BOD, and COD, as well as the greatest DO, of the four upstream locations in both seasons. Tilganga had the greatest BOD and COD in both seasons, while Teku Dovan had the highest COD and lowest DO post-monsoon among the downstream locations.

Most of the seven locations' water quality has improved since 2013, according to the data, which were compared to those of ENPHO. There was little difference in pH readings for either of the two seasons across the five years that data was analyzed. However, water during the monsoon season was shown to be more acidic than water during the post-monsoon season for each year. BOD fell from 2012 to 2014 and remained almost the same in 2019 when Gaurighat was used as a sample of the four upstream, relatively protected regions; COD declined from 2012 to 2014 but climbed in 2019. From 2012 forward, both BOD and COD dropped in Tripureshwar, which represents the more disturbed, downstream regions. In the monsoon season, Gaurighat had lower BOD and COD levels than Tripureshwar every year except 2012 and 2019; in the post-monsoon season, Gaurighat had considerably lower BOD and COD values every year.

Because so many elements influence water quality, it's impossible to trace seasonal and year-to-year variations to any one factor.

Limitation of the study

The study's key shortcoming was that it only looked and examined secondary sources of data collected by other researchers and GON. Because the data's authenticity, precision, and correctness are uncertain, it's possible that it's not very scientific. Similarly, data was acquired from several sources, reducing the data's coherency and homology.

6.3 Recommendation

The Bagmati Cleanup Campaign should be continued and expanded to its tributaries, based on the general improvement in water quality. The Dhap Dam, which has a capacity of 85000 m3 and is part of the BRBIP's second phase, should be finished on schedule. During the pre- and post-monsoon seasons, it will release water to remove pollutants from the river and keep the DO at the Pasupatinath Temple at a safe level for bathing. The cleanup of other formerly filthy rivers, such as the Kallang, Quinhua, Rhine, and Thames, demonstrates the need of solid waste and wastewater management. Rehabilitation and restoration of the five existing WWTPs shown in Table 1-1, as well as a more robust residential waste collecting system, would be critical.

The water quality of the Bagmati River has been studied by many people, groups, and organizations. Data collection, on the other hand,

appears to be disorganized; sample locations and sampling frequencies are uneven; and data from different research are not comparable. It is critical to standardize test methodologies and gather consistent data in order to compare results across time and locations. It could be beneficial if GON set up monitoring stations along the Bagmati River to collect and analyze samples at regular intervals for the essential parameters and keep a database. Researchers will be able to more properly evaluate water quality and identify variables that cause changes in the water with better data.

References

- Adhikari, S. (2016). Bagmati Clean-Up Campaign: A Greater Initiative. Retrieved from <https://tunza.eco-generation.org/resourcesView.jsp?boardID=ambassadorReport&viewID=41749>
- Asian Development Bank. (2017, 9/19/2019). Bagmati River Basin Improvement Project - Additional Financing. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/projects/43448-015/main>
- Bajracharya, S. B. (2009). Bagmati Action Plan (2009–2014) (M. Banskota, P. K. Jha, K. Thapa, D. Joshi, & R. R. Timsina Eds.). Kathmandu, Nepal: Government of Nepal & National Trust for Nature Conservation
- Batra, A. (2015). Darkling waters. DownToEarth. Retrieved from <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/darkling-waters-34115>
- Bhandari, B., Joshi, L., Shrestha, P., & Nakarmi, P. (2017). Water quality of Bagmati river in Kathmandu valley: 2011–2014. *Journal of Environment and Public Health*, 1(1), 65–73. Retrieved from <http://enpho.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/ENPHO-Journal-V1-II.pdf>
- Bosch, J. M., & Hewlett, J. D. (1982). A review of catchment experiments to determine the effect of vegetation changes on water yield and evapotranspiration. *Journal of Hydrology*, 55(1–4), 3–23. doi:10.1016/0022-1694(82)90117-2
- CEMAT Consultants. (2000). Report on surface water quality monitoring works of Kathmandu Valley. Urban Water Supply Reforms in the Kathmandu Valley Project.
- Dahal, A., Khanal, M., & Ale, M. (2011). Bagmati River Festival: Conservation of Degrading Rivert. Paper presented at the 2011 Georgia Water Resources Conference, University of Georgia. <http://hdl.handle.net/1853/46295>
- Hardach, S. (2015). How the River Thames was brought back from the dead. BBC Britain. Retrieved from <http://www.bbc.com/earth/story/20151111-how-the-river-thames-was-brought-back-fromthe-dead>
- Health and Environmental Management Society. (2016). Assessment of Land Cover and its Contribution to Runoff Response in Watershed to aid land use planning for sustainable landscape: A Pilot Research Study in Small Watersheds of Tanahun and Kaski Districts. USAID and WWF grant number AID–367–A–11–00003
- Kannel, P. R., Lee, S., Kanel, S. R., Kahn, S. P., & Lee, Y.-S. (2007). Spatial–temporal variation and comparative assessment of water qualities of urban river system: a case study of the river Bagmati (Nepal). *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 129(1–3), 433–459. doi:10.1007/s10661-006-9375-6
- Kathmandu Upatyaka Khanepani Limited, Ministry of Urban Development, & Government of Nepal. (2013). Kathmandu Valley Wastewater Management Project. Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/project-document/76140/34304-043-nep-iec-01.pdf>
- Kathmandu Valley Environment Outlook. (2007). (G. Rana, A. B. Murray, D. R. Maharjan, & A. K. Thaku Eds.). Kathmandu, Nepal: International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development
- NWCF. (2009). The Bagmati: Issues, Challenges and Prospects. Kathmandu, Nepal: Nepal Water Conservation Foundation and National Trust for Nature Conservation.
- Odum, E. P. (1971). *Fundamentals of Ecology* (3rd ed.). Philadelphia, Pennsylvania: Saunders.
- Pandey, S. (2005). Water pollution and health. *Kathmandu University Medical Journal*, 4, 128–134.
- Prajapati, G. R. (2015). Participatory Approach of Bagmati River Conservation and its Present Status of Water Quality. (M. Sc.). Pokhara University, Pokhara, Nepal.
- Project Administration Manual for Nepal: Bagmati River Basin Improvement Project. (2013). Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/project-document/79350/43448-013-pam.pdf>
- Singapore Infopedia (2019). Clean-up of Singapore River and Kallang Basin. Retrieved from https://eresources.nlb.gov.sg/infopedia/articles/SIP_2019-05-21_104327.html
- Urban Pathways. (2020). Nepal - Kathmandu. Retrieved from <https://www.urban-pathways.org/kathmandu.html>
- Vaidya, S. R. (2017). Status of Bagmati River before and after cleaning campaign in Kathmandu valley. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Education and Research*, 2(4), 85–88. doi:10.22271/multieducation
- G. Rana, A. B. Murray, D. R. Maharjan, & A. K. Thaku Eds (2007). Kathmandu Valley Environment Outlook.